

Accelerator Control Using Gaussian Process-Model Predictive Control (GP-MPC)

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Author:
Su Lei Aye

CERN
BE-CSS-DSB

SUPERVISOR(S):
Verena Kain
Michael Schenk

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

GP-MPC (Gaussian Process - Model Predictive Control) is a sophisticated control strategy to make informed decisions in control software systems. GPs are employed to model the dynamic behavior of the controlled system, monitoring not only expected responses but also uncertainties associated with the system reactions. GP-MPC starts by associating the system's relationship between control inputs and outputs using GPs. These GPs are probabilistic models that predict the future system states over a specified prediction horizon. At each time step, an optimization problem is solved by the acquisition function to compute the optimal control inputs for this prediction horizon, aiming to find the global minima while adhering to system constraints.

ABSTRACT

This project aims to develop a GP-MPC (Gaussian Process-Model Predictive Control) approach, for controlling accelerator systems using Machine Learning. By leveraging insufficient data and uncertainty quantification capabilities of Gaussian Processes, the algorithm will overcome limitations related to beam instrumentation and training large iterations. The final outcome will be the implementation of the GP-MPC towards integration into CERN's Generic Optimisation Framework, facilitating easy deployment for operational scenarios and enabling intelligent accelerator control.

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1. Introduction

This project aims to enhance the control of accelerator systems using a special machine learning approach called Gaussian Process Model Predictive Control (GP-MPC), which is in some ways similar to model-based Reinforcement Learning (RL).. Accelerator systems help particles move at high speeds, and we want to use GP-MPC to make them work more efficiently and accurately.

However, there are a few challenges that will need to be considered such as having high sample efficiency (the amount of training data needed), including uncertainty and risk estimates, and not having sufficient beam instrumentation available to define a proper Markovian state.

Using GP-MPC can help develop dynamics (transition) and reward models for the problem under consideration without requiring heavy amounts of data. It can furthermore provide a measure of prediction confidence.

The ultimate goal of this GP-MPC project is to implement and test the algorithms that can overcome the challenges and design the code with the idea in mind to make it compatible with CERN's Generic Optimisation Framework for the real-world scenarios. This will create a more efficient and accurate control system that can benefit scientific research and particle acceleration.

2. Setting Up AWAKE environment

To begin, we initialize the setup of the AWAKE (Advanced Proton Driven Plasma Wakefield Acceleration Experiment) environment on the CERN machine for use in the Gaussian Process Model framework. This environment, implemented as the library in Python, serves as a critical component of the research framework. It simulates the behavior of the AWAKE particle accelerator at CERN, providing a controlled platform for all sorts of control algorithms. The environment defines the state and action spaces,

calculates particle trajectories and accelerator responses, and enables the study of the impact of various actions on the accelerator's performance.

3. Base Models

There are two base models we used before implementing GP-MPC algorithms. Those are called Transition Model and Rewards Model. Transition Model takes state and action (`state_action`) as inputs to learn to predict the next states (`next_states`). Rewards Model takes next states (`next_states`) as input to learn to predict expected reward (`reward`).

3.1. Transition Model

The Transition Model involves learning how the environment changes when the agent takes specific actions based on the current state. By predicting the next states (future outcomes), this model allows the agent to plan and optimize its actions for better rewards and safety, all before actually executing these actions in the real world. By using Gaussian Processes, the Transition Model can help understand complicated connections between different beam observations and what happens in the accelerator. This way of modeling helps the computer program predict what will happen when we do different things in the accelerator. It helps us make smart choices to get the results we want when controlling the accelerator. It's a crucial method for effective decision-making and strategy development. As in Figure 1, the observed next state falls within the predicted next state confidence interval. This suggests that the model is capable of predicting satisfactory outcomes thus far.

Figure. 1: Transition model: (state, action) -> predict next_state

3.2. Reward Model

The Reward Model, on the other hand, complements the Transition Model in the agent's decision-making process. While the Transition Model focuses on understanding how the environment evolves based on the agent's actions, the Reward Model evaluates the desirability of these outcomes. It assigns rewards to next states to keep on going, providing a quantitative measure of how good or bad they are in achieving the agent's objectives. The Reward Model enables the agent to learn which actions lead to higher rewards and, consequently, guides it towards making choices that maximize its cumulative rewards over time. In the context of the accelerator, the Reward Model plays a role in helping the agent discern between favorable and unfavorable outcomes, ultimately aiding in the formulation of optimal strategies for accelerator control. It serves as a crucial component for control algorithms, driving the agent towards making decisions that align with its goals and objectives. Show in Figure 2, where the agent's choices are influenced by the expected rewards associated with different actions.

Figure. 2: Reward model: next_state -> reward

4. Gaussian Process Model

In this session, we will break down the entire process, explaining how it unfolded step by step.

4.1. Utilization of Acquisition Function

In this section, we focus on developing an acquisition function that helps choose actions and improve the system's performance in a fixed state. The acquisition function takes a list of action values as input, reshapes them into a trajectory of actions over the given horizon, and computes the cumulative acquisition value. This acquisition value is based on predictions of next states, rewards, and eventually on their associated uncertainties. The acquisition function plays a crucial role in the optimization process, guiding the selection of actions that maximize the expected cumulative reward. By effectively utilizing this acquisition function we can make informed decisions on how to adjust accelerator parameters to achieve optimal outcomes in an environment.

4.2. Determination of the best Optimizer

After having the acquisition function implemented, we emphasize on determining the best optimizer for the task at hand. During each iteration, the acquisition function is employed to assess potential actions and their expected rewards. Subsequently, the optimizer is utilized to pinpoint the best action based on these predictions, updating the Gaussian Process models accordingly with newly collected data samples. We specifically use PyBOBYQA optimization method to identify the optimal action trajectory because it can find the closest best action that maximizes the expected cumulative reward. The chosen action is then applied in the real environment to observe its impact on the system's state and reward. This iterative process helps refine the models and improve the accuracy of reward predictions, ultimately contributing to the overall efficiency of our approach.

4.3. Unifying Controller Function

From there, we combine everything together into the controller function to evaluate the performance of different control strategies. Using a range of random steps as a parameter, the controller function assesses the effectiveness of control actions within the AWAKE accelerator simulation. It records episode lengths, evaluates success rates, and plots the results, providing valuable insights into the control strategies' impact on the system. This evaluation process is crucial for unifying and optimizing the controller function to achieve enhanced performance and efficiency in accelerator operations. By comparing controller performance to random actions over multiple episodes, this section aims to provide insights into the controller's ability to steer the system effectively and achieve desired outcomes.

5. Real Life Application on Accelerator Control

According to Figure 3, the environment describes the trajectory of the AWAKE electron beam as it is brought from its source to the plasma cell. There are 10 position monitors along the line as well as 10 correctors. With our algorithm we want to use the position measurement to automatically and best decide how to adjust the correctors to bring the trajectory closer to zero. This is to avoid large beam excursions and potential particle losses.

Figure. 3: Electron beam line of the CERN AWAKE environment

5.1 One step ahead, horizon = 1

In this section of the report, we focus on the "one step ahead" approach with a horizon of 1 in the context of accelerator control for the AWAKE project. The goal here is

to utilize real-time position measurements obtained from the position monitors along the electron beam's trajectory. By analyzing the current position, our algorithm swiftly calculates the necessary adjustments for the correctors. These adjustments are aimed at minimizing the deviation of the electron beam from its desired trajectory, bringing it closer to zero. This immediate correction is crucial in preventing abrupt beam excursions and potential particle losses. This approach ensures that the beam's trajectory is constantly aligned with the desired path, enhancing stability and minimizing disruptions.

5.2 More than one step ahead, horizon > 1

In this section, we delve into a more sophisticated approach to accelerator control in the AWAKE project. Instead of focusing solely on the immediate next step, we extend our perspective by considering a horizon greater than 1. This means we take into account multiple future steps along the trajectory. By analyzing the data from the position monitors, our algorithm predicts the potential deviations of the electron beam over these future steps. This allows us to make calculated adjustments to the correctors that not only correct the present position but also anticipate and counteract deviations that could occur over several steps.

By employing both the "one step ahead" and the "more than one step ahead" strategies, we are equipped to effectively manage different environments.

6. Results

As for the outcome, Figure 4 shows the results of the very first iteration, after combining the transition model and reward models using our acquisition function to find the best action to maximize rewards and minimize risks. It shows that the observed reward and predicted reward are not very close, as the difference between them is large. This is because the model has not had enough data to learn from and to adjust its parameters accordingly.

Figure 5 shows the results after 18 iterations. In this case, the observed reward and predicted reward are much closer, indicating that the model has become more accurate at predicting rewards. This is because the model has had more samples to learn from and to adjust its parameters accordingly.

The results suggest that the model is able to accurately predict rewards after a certain number of iterations. This is important, as it means that the model can be used to make decisions that maximize rewards and minimize risks.

```
Initial true reward -0.22491701117210205
Initial pred. reward -0.6606791
ITERATION: 0
Current state: tensor([-0.0222, -0.0496, -0.0729, -0.1020, -0.1755,  0.2035,  0.4620,  0.3629,
                       0.2181,  0.1493])
Best action: [0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0.]
Next state: [-0.02216892 -0.04955467 -0.07285278 -0.10200015 -0.17547456  0.20349273
             0.4620307  0.36290238  0.21806641  0.14931128]
Reward: -0.224917011172102
Reward (pred): -0.6605854034423828
```

Figure. 4: First Iteration Results

```
ITERATION: 18
Current state: [-0.02216892 -0.04955467 -0.07285278 -0.10200015 -0.17547456  0.20349273
              0.4620307  0.36290238  0.21806641  0.14931128]
Best action: [-1.43790405e-04  7.53724006e-04 -6.40631093e-04 -6.73291034e-04
              5.24910777e-04 -7.68504165e-05  2.63739254e-04  3.77769772e-04
              -1.37776166e-04 -5.93227664e-05]
Next state: [-0.02217285 -0.04954173 -0.07284082 -0.10200222 -0.17548277  0.20349988
             0.46205418  0.36293105  0.21810425  0.1493685 ]
Reward: -0.22493467551064225
Reward (pred): -0.22495219111442566
```

Figure. 5: Eighteenth Iteration Results

Shown in Figure 6, 7 and 8, observe the study of the convergence behavior of the GP-MPC algorithm vs number of initial data points (random samples) for three different horizons ($h = 1, 3,$ and $5,$ respectively). The top plot shows the average episode length, that is, the number of iterations needed to reach the objective and the error bars indicate the standard deviation. The bottom plot illustrates in how many of the evaluation episodes the algorithm failed to reach the objective. An episode is considered a failure

whenever the algorithm does not reach the objective in less than 30 iterations (n_steps_max). The studies were performed over 30 evaluation episodes ($n_episodes_eval$) to obtain some statistics. The results demonstrate the high sample efficiency of GP-MPC. With as little as five random samples to initialize the GPs, the average episode length already drops down to two iterations. It reaches optimal behavior (one step to reach the target) with only twelve initial samples. Beyond that, there is no additional benefit in adding more samples to initialize the GPs.

Figure. 6: Number of iterations needed to reach the objective and Failed to reach the objective on horizon = 1

Figure. 7: Number of iterations needed to reach the objective and Failed to reach the objective on horizon = 3

Figure. 8: Number of iterations needed to reach the objective and Failed to reach the objective on horizon = 5

7. Future Works and Improvements

In this section, the focus is on potential future works and improvements related to propagating Gaussian process errors.

- How to propagate a Gaussian Process error

Next step is to enhance the Gaussian process modeling by addressing the propagation of errors. This includes exploring the implementation of Taylor Approximation, which may involve referencing relevant research papers and notes for guidance. Additionally, the integration of the BoTorch library is suggested to change models and effectively propagate errors within the Gaussian process framework, potentially improving predictive accuracy and uncertainty estimation.

- Safety Constraints

Meanwhile, we also need to consider safety constraints. As for future work, we will delve into strategies and methodologies for incorporating these safety constraints into our framework. These constraints serve as protective measures, preventing the system from venturing into unsafe states. By implementing well-defined boundaries, limits, and checks, we aim to enhance the system's resilience to safer and more reliable real-world applications.

- Changing the environment for horizon >1

As part of our ongoing efforts, we are actively exploring the possibility of identifying an environment that aligns more suitably with the "More Than One Step Ahead, Horizon > 1" approach. Since using AWAKE's trajectory environment might be not fully compatible with the horizon above 1, we are currently employing it for testing purposes. Despite any compatibility limitations, utilizing the AWAKE setup for testing provides a valuable opportunity to refine and debug our algorithm. This enables us to fine-tune the code and gain insights into its behavior, paving the way for potential adaptation or integration with environments that better suit its predictive capabilities.

- **Make it Compatible with CERN's Optimization Framework**

In the content of the procedure, the final updated algorithms should be prepared for packaging and integration into CERN's Generic Optimisation Framework and should prioritize compatibility to ensure effortless deployment and operational adaptability in various scenarios. This strategic approach aims to facilitate smooth implementation and maximize the algorithm's effectiveness within the framework for optimal outcome.

Overall, these future works and improvements indicate a commitment to refining and advancing the modeling and control techniques discussed in the preceding sections, with a focus on accuracy, and safety.

8. Conclusion

To conclude, we managed to accomplish a model-based control algorithm grounded in the GP-MPC framework for intelligent accelerator control, addressing challenges associated with limited data availability and the need for uncertainty quantification in beam instrumentation. Throughout this project, we have precisely constructed foundational base models, including transition and reward models, based on Gaussian Processes. The creation of a tailored AWAKE environment, coupled with the strategic application of acquisition functions and optimizers, has played a pivotal role in shaping our intelligent controller. Whether predicting one step ahead or multiple steps ahead, it has consistently showcased its ability to optimize beam acceleration and system efficiency. These promising results underscore its potential for real-life applications in accelerator physics and beyond. This collaborative effort is not only a testament to the dedication of our team but also a testament to the potential for this cutting-edge approach to transform complex systems with the inherent uncertainties for accelerator control.

9. Acknowledgments

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10. References

- [1] BE-CSS-DSB. (n.d.). *CERN Accelerating science*. Gitlab.
<https://gitlab.cern.ch/dsb/prototypes/gp-mpc-dev>
- [2] Girard, A. (n.d.). Approximate Methods for Propagation of Uncertainty with Gaussian Process Models. <https://www.dcs.gla.ac.uk/~rod/publications/Gir04.pdf>
- [3] Kamthe, S., & Deisenroth, M. P. (2018, February 22). *Data-Efficient Reinforcement Learning with Probabilistic Model Predictive Control*. arXiv.org.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1706.06491>
- [4] Schenk, M., Combarro, E. F., Grossi, M., Kain, V., Li, K. S. B., Popa, M.-M., & Vallecorsa, S. (2022, September 22). *Hybrid actor-critic algorithm for Quantum Reinforcement Learning at CERN Beam Lines*. arXiv.org.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.11044>